

STUDY ON TRUSS TYPE SEGMENTAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURE FOR TEMPORARY RESCUE BRIDGE

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Introduction

(a) Typhoon Morakot, 2009

(b) the Chi-Chi Earthquake, 1999

Damage to bridges and disaster rescue needed

(a) the construction stage

(b) the commissioning and completion stage

Concept of a temporary composite bridge for emergency disaster relief

Improve stiffness of long span bridge !

(a) construction of weight-balance structural module

(b) construction of crossing structural module

Construction sequence of temporary rescue composite bridge

Working above the river

Improve worker safety for bridge !

Design of truss type composite bridge

FEM model of 50-m span asymmetric truss type segmental cable-stayed bridge

Truss type girders and structural segment (unit: mm)

Meet the design requirement for deflection-to-span ratio

Shape deformation

Deformation of shape (various loading position)

Experiment of truss type bridge segment

Assemble of truss type main girder

Experiment setup for flexural test

Comparison for deformation shape (applied load of P = 20-50 kN)

Comparison for force-deflection curve (stiffness) of specimen

Validate the accuracy of FEM model

Construction operational efficiency analysis & Conclusions

Cantilever erection method for rescue bridge construction (with a mini-crawler crane)

Incremental launching method for bridge (assembly on river side then push forward)

Construction time analysis for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge

Manpower analysis for 50-m span temporary rescue bridge

- (1) the truss type segmental composite bridge improve the stiffness of 50-m span rescue bridge to meet the design requirement
- (2) autonomous assembly technology for bridge construction has a significant contribution to improving the worker safety and shortening assembly time of the rescue bridge
- (3) the incremental launching method has more operational efficiency than the cantilever erection method
- (4) the incremental launching method could prevent workers from constructing above the river and should be more secure for safety